

THE EFFECT OF HOLE DISTANCES FOR STATIC AND FATIGUE BEHAVIORS OF GR/EPOXY COMPOSITE MATERIALS WITH PATCH REPAIR

Ming-Chuen Yip, Chih-Han Yang and Tsai-Chih Chien

*Department of Power Mechanical Engineering, National Tsing Hua University
Hsinchu, Taiwan 300, R. O. C.*

ABSTRACT

Composite materials are widely used in many industries; during fabrication process it may cause damage inside the materials, also when the materials subjected to static or fatigue loadings during operating, unavoidable defect may occurs. The investigation of static and fatigue characteristic of drilled-hole composite laminates for different hole distance was studied in this paper. The composite plate was formed by $[0/+45/90/-45]_{2s}$ lay up, two horizontal holes of 3 mm diameter was drilled on the specimen. The center to center distances between two holes are chosen 6, 8 and 10 mm. In addition, repair efficiency was also investigated for static and fatigue strength. For static tensile loading, it would reduce the static strength on specimen due to the stress concentration and fiber breakage related problems, and the strength decreases with the hole distance decrease. For the fatigue analysis, the fatigue life for the drilled-hole specimens and repaired specimens were shorter than the original specimens.

KEYWORDS: static strength, fatigue strength, hole distance, patch repair

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials can be used in aviation and automobile related industries. However, it is possible to suffer the un-avoidable defect problem during fabrication process and to cause damage when subjecting to static or reciprocated loadings during operating stage. In addition, drilled-holes are normally needed for composite components when designing a structure, matching wires through composites or connecting the structures. Circular holes are commonly adopted because it is easier for drilling and for mitigating the stress concentration problem. When the composite structure used for an operating period, micro damage must occur in the component, repair methods are oven used for extending the usage life of composite component if the degree of damage does not impact to its safety [1-3], and patch repair method was commonly used in composite laminates.

Ellyin [4] propose that under the high fatigue loading of frequency, $\pm 45^\circ$ cross-ply

composite of each relying mainly on matrix, the fatigue-life diagram is similar to the typical creep curve, with the increase of frequency in high load, because the existence of some hot and stress, make the periodic creep increase. In 1986, Hwang and Han [5] showed that the S-N curve of the carbon fiber composites can be fitted by a straight line in semi-log plot, and the equation of the curve can be written:

$$S = a + b \log N_f \quad (1)$$

where S is the stress range, N_f is the number of cycles to failure, b is a constant and the slope of S- N_f curve, a is a constant and the intercept of S- N_f curve.

In this paper, experimental method is used to evaluate the effect of hole distances for the static and fatigue behaviors of Gr/Epoxy composite materials, the laminates has total of 16 layers and was drilled with two horizontal 3mm holes on the specimen, in order to investigate the effect of static and fatigue characteristic acting on specimen for different hole distance and repair method. In addition, single and double sides patch repaired composites are also tested to evaluate the improvement of static and fatigue strength.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Gr/Epoxy composite materials are selected to be the testing materials of this study, the specimen was made of uniform laminated plate of total 16 layers with $[0/+45/90/-45]_{2s}$ lay up, two 3mm circular holes are drilled in the center part of the specimen, the configuration of the specimen is shown in figure 1. The hole distance between center to center are selected to be 6, 8 and 10 mm, all repair plate are made by 4 plies unidirectional composite laminates of $25 \times 25 \text{ mm}^2$, and the repair plates was patched on the hole region.

Fig 1 Configuration of specimen

The experiment flow chat is shown in Figure 2. There are eight types of specimen: original specimen (OR), drilled holes specimen with hole distance 6, 8 and 10mm (HD6mm, HD8mm, HD10mm), single-side patch repaired specimen with hole distances 6, 8 and 10mm (RHD6mm, RHD8mm, RHD10mm), and double-sides patch repaired specimen with hole distance 6mm (D-RHD6mm).

The static test and fatigue test procedures were carried out by ASTM D3039-95a [6] and

ASTM D3479-96 [7] standard requirement, respectively. All static and fatigue tests were performed by Instron's 1322 servohydraulic testing system, quasistatic test speed were used for static experiments, sinusoidal wave form with frequency of 5 Hz are used for fatigue tests until the specimen broken. Single and double side repaired specimen are both used for testing to compare the repair efficiency of the composites. In each same testing condition, at least 5 specimen were tested for static and fatigue strength.

Fig 2 Experiment flow chats

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Static tensile test

The static strength of eight types of specimen is shown in Figure 3, the average static strength of original composite plate is 781.33 MPa, and the strengths for specimen with hole distances 6, 8 and 10 mm are 634.70 to 602.09 MPa, respectively, which decreases with the hole distance decrease. As shown in Figure 4, due to the stress concentration effects for both holes, the stress amplitude increases with the hole distance decrease by superposition

ERROR: rangecheck
OFFENDING COMMAND: .buildcmap

STACK:

-dictionary-
/WinCharSetFFFF-V2TT9BF4ACCA
/CMap
-dictionary-
/WinCharSetFFFF-V2TT9BF4ACCA